

Synthesis of 5-Aryl/Aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2-Thiones and Related Compounds as Possible Fungicides

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Eight 5-aryl/aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione (I), eleven 3-hydroxybenzyl-5-aryl/aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione (II) and twenty *N,N'*-bis-(3-methylene/ethyleno-5-aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione)-phenylenediamines/benzidines (III) have been prepared to study their antifungal activity. Most of them have been screened against two pathogenic fungi, *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae* and found to be fungicidal.

THE oxadiazole ring is well known for its biological activities. Some 3-alkyl/phenyl carbamates of substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones are reported as bactericides¹. Several benzidine derivatives are also found to possess antimicrobial² and fungicidal³ activities. Keeping these in view the title compounds have been prepared.

5-Aryl/aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (I) were prepared by the reaction of aryl/aryloxyacyl hydrazines⁴ with carbondisulfide in the presence of alkali⁵. I were condensed with benzaldehyde to give corresponding 3-hydroxybenzyl-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (II). Reaction of I with aldehydes in the presence of phenylenediamine/benzidine gave corresponding *N,N'*-bis-(3,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione) - phenylenediamines/benzidines respectively. The compounds were characterised by their elemental analyses and IR spectra.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr.

5-Aryl/aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones⁶ (I): To an ethanolic (95%, 200 ml) solution of aryl/aryloxyacylhydrazine⁴ (0.05 M), KOH (0.05 M), and carbondisulfide (1 M) were added and the resulting solution was refluxed for 6 hr. It was concentrated to a small volume, poured into ice-water and filtered. The filtrate on acidification

gave a precipitate which was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The properties and analysis of oxadiazole-2-thiones are recorded in Table 1.

3-Hydroxybenzyl-5-aryl/aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (II): 5-Aryl/aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione (I), dissolved in ethanol (0.01 M), was cooled in an ice-bath. Benzaldehyde (0.01 M) was added to this. The mixture was kept in an ice-bath for 3 hr. The solid separating out was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised. The properties and analysis of II are given in Table 2.

***N,N'*-Bis-(3-methylene/ethyleno-5-aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione) - phenylenediamines/benzidines (III):** 5-Aryloxyalkyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione (I), dissolved in ethanol (0.01 M), was cooled in an ice-bath. To this, formaldehyde/acetaldehyde (0.01 M) was added. An ethanolic solution of phenylenediamine/benzidine (0.005 M) was now added to it dropwise with swirling. The mixture was kept in an ice-bath for 3 hr. The solid separating out was filtered, washed and recrystallised with aqueous ethanol. The properties and analysis of III are given in Table 3.

Fungicidal activity: The compounds were screened for their fungicidal activity against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae* by agar plate technique^{6,7}.

In general, compounds screened are more active towards *A. flavus* than *H. oryzae*. Compounds of Table 3 are more fungicidal than the parent oxadiazoles. The presence of phenoxy moiety at position-5 of oxadiazole ring increases the antifungal activity. Introduction of hydroxybenzyl group at position-3 also slightly increases the activity. There is no significant effect towards the fungicidal activity by introduction of benzidine moiety in place of phenylenediamine. The best antifungal compounds of this series are 21, 29, 32 and 38 having 5-*p*-chlorophenoxy moiety in the oxadiazole ring. All these observations are based on their comparison

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TABLE 1— 5-ARYL/ARYLOXYALKYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONES (I)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	Antifungal activity Conc. 1 : 100,000	
						<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
1. ^a	4-HO-C ₆ H ₄	208	74.6	14.15 (14.43)	16.27 (16.49)	—	—
2.	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	300	72.8	—	11.76 (11.94)	21.6	13.5
3.	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₃	180	74.5	—	12.44 (12.64)	23.4	15.7
4.	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ -O-CH ₃	136	78.7	—	13.38 (13.56)	—	—
5.	2-(CH ₃) ₂ CH-5-CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₃	113	72.6	10.24 (10.60)	11.94 (12.12)	38.2	29.4
6.	2-ClC ₆ H ₄ -O-CH (CH ₃)	90	63.0	—	12.28 (12.47)	—	—
7. ^b	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ -O-CH (CH ₃)	114-15	62.8	—	12.26 (12.47)	39.5	31.2
8.	4-CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH (CH ₃)	135-37	67.7	—	13.40 (13.56)	28.0	17.3

a. $\nu_{\max}$ 825 (*p*-substituted benzene), 1070 (C=S), 1600 (C=N) cm⁻¹.

b. $\nu_{\max}$ 750 (C-Cl), 830 (*p*-substituted benzene), 1080 (C=S), 1230 (=C-O-C), 1620 (C=N) cm⁻¹.

TABLE 2— 3-HYDROXYBENZYL-5-ARYL/ARYLOXYALKYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONES (II)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	N% Found (Calcd.)	S% Found (Calcd.)	Antifungal activity Conc. 1 : 100,000	
						<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
9.	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	145	68.2	—	10.56 (10.74)	—	—
10.	3-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	122	65.5	—	10.52 (10.74)	—	—
11.	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	180	68.8	9.08 (9.39)	10.58 (10.74)	20.0	12.8
12. ^c	C ₆ H ₅ -O-CH ₂	95	72.2	—	9.98 (10.19)	22.7	15.4
13.	2-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₂	92	74.6	—	9.53 (9.75)	—	—
14.	3-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₂	82	67.8	—	9.50 (9.75)	22.9	15.7
15.	4-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₂	104	70.5	—	9.48 (9.75)	23.2	16.0
16.	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₂	118	75.0	—	9.30 (9.18)	—	—
17.	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₂	137	76.4	7.75 (8.03)	9.00 (9.18)	44.0	33.3
18.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl.C ₆ H ₃ -O-CH ₂	85	67.4	—	8.65 (8.82)	46.4	36.2
19.	2,4(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃ -O-CH ₂	150	66.8	—	9.21 (9.35)	—	—

c. $\nu_{\max}$ 750 (monosubstituted benzene), 1075 (C=S), 1240 (=C-O-C), 1600 (C=N) cm⁻¹.

TABLE 3— N,N'-Bis-(3-METHYLENO/ETHYLENO-5-ARYLOXYALKYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONE)-PHENYLENE-DIAMINES/BENZIDINES (III)

Sl. No.	R	R'	X	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)	Antifungal activity Conc. 1 : 100,000	
							<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
20.	2-Cl	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	118	68.1	S 9.66 (9.86)	48.4	36.0
21. ^d	4-Cl	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	147	65.3	S 9.64 (9.86)	50.2	36.4
22.	4-OH ₂	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	139	59.2	S 10.38 (10.59) N 13.64 (13.90)	28.3	24.7
23.	2-Cl	H	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	Decomp.	52.6	S 9.62 (9.86)	—	—

(Table 3 contd.)

24.	4-Cl	H	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	Decomp.	43.3	S 9.64 (9.86)	47.1	36.2
25.	4-CH ₃	H	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	>250	46.3	S 10.38 (10.59)	-	-
26.	4-Cl	H	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	87	71.2	S 9.66 (9.86)	45.3	34.4
27.	4-CH ₃	H	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	112	79.4	S 10.40 (10.59)	-	-
28.	2-Cl	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	141	45.4	S 8.63 (8.87)	-	-
29.	4-Cl	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	152	93.6	S 8.66 (8.87) N 11.37 (11.65)	50.8	35.6
30.	4-CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	51	81.1	S 9.22 (9.41)	29.0	25.0
31.	2-Cl	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	107	45.0	S 9.25 (9.45)	-	-
32.	4-Cl	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	129	44.7	S 9.22 (9.45)	51.0	36.2
33.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	122	48.0	S 9.96 (10.12) N 13.00 (13.29)	28.8	24.5
34.	2-Cl	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	Gum	62.0	-	-	-
35.	4-Cl	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	103	53.4	S 9.27 (9.45)	47.7	36.4
36.	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	Gum	48.6	-	-	-
37.	2-Cl	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	112	78.9	S 8.72 (8.53)	-	-
38.	4-Cl	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	66	79.0	S 8.74 (8.53)	51.4	36.0
39.*	4-CH ₃	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄ (NH) ₂	129	67.8	S 9.18 (9.04)	29.2	25.8
							75.4	87.4
							85.5	80.7

d. $\nu_{\max}$ 740 (C-Cl), 810 (*p*-substituted benzene), 1230 (=C-O-C-), 1650 (C=N), 3350 (NH) cm⁻¹.

e. $\nu_{\max}$ 810 (*p*-substituted benzene), 1225 (=C-O-C-), 1640 (C=N), 3300 (NH) cm⁻¹.

against two commercial fungicides Memcge and Blitox 50 WP.

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